

A longitudinal study of *Toxoplasma gondii* seroconversion on four large Danish sow farms

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ABSTRACT

Serological tests are routinely used to detect *Toxoplasma gondii* specific IgG antibodies in serum. Serological surveys of *T. gondii* show a medium to high prevalence in Danish indoor sows at the time of slaughter. However, little is known about when sows acquire *T. gondii*, and for how long they remain seropositive. Our focus was on quantifying the incidence rates in different age-cohorts and on investigating the *T. gondii* IgG antibody dynamics in sows. Four large Danish sow farms were longitudinally surveyed for 1 year. A total of 320 animals from 6, 12, 18, and 24-months age-cohorts were sampled at 5-week intervals. In total, 2989 plasma samples were tested using commercial enzyme linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA). The incidence rate in each of the four age-cohorts was calculated, and a time-to-event analysis was applied to the interval censored data to investigate the relationship between age and probability of *T. gondii* seroconversion. In the initial ELISA testing, eight sows tested positive for *T. gondii* at first survey, of which seven remained seropositive throughout the follow-up period. Additionally, 16 sows seroconverted, but only five of these remained seropositive. Weekly incidence rates in the 6, 12, 18, and 24-month age-cohorts were 0.0017 (95% CI = 0.0008 – 0.0037), 0.0009 (95% CI = 0.0003 – 0.0027), 0.0003 (95% CI = 0.0000 – 0.0018), and 0.0023 (95% CI = 0.0010 – 0.0051), respectively. Time-to-event analysis suggested that the incidence rate increased with age but could not conclude this definitively. The retesting of a subsample of the sows (n = 200) with the same ELISA and with modified direct agglutination test (MAT), and western blot (WB) assays suggested that 12 out of the 24 initial ELISA seropositive sows may have been false positive. These 12 sows also showed fluctuating antibody dynamics in ELISA. Hence, the unstable antibody dynamics in ELISA may pose a challenge for serological surveys of *T. gondii* in sows.

1. Introduction

Toxoplasma gondii is an opportunistic protozoan parasite, infecting a wide range of host species (Webster and Dubey, 2010). Cats are the only known definitive hosts of *T. gondii*, and during the infection stage, they shed oocysts in their feces for 3–10 days after ingesting tissue cysts, and for 18 days or longer after ingesting oocysts (Dubey, 2009a). *T. gondii* is

present on pig farms worldwide (Dubey, 2009b; Dubey et al., 2020). The horizontal transmissions to pigs can be caused by ingestion of oocysts in feed or water or tissue cysts in rodents (Dubey, 2009b; Ortega-Pacheco et al., 2013; Dubey et al., 2020). Seropositivity in pigs is known to be associated with risk factors such as outdoor production, small farm size (< 400 finishing pigs), age of animals (i.e., sows), presence of cats on farms, and a lack of rodent control (Kijlstra et al., 2004; Ortega-Pacheco

Abbreviations: CI, confidence interval; ELISA, enzyme linked immunosorbent assay; JAGS, just another Gibbs sampler; MAT, modified agglutination test; SPF, specific pathogen free; WB, western blot.

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et al., 2013; Djokic et al., 2016; Limon et al., 2017; Olsen et al., 2020).

In pigs, IgM antibodies appear approximately 1-week post infection, followed by IgG antibodies, which become predominant after approximately 2-weeks of infection (Lind et al., 1997; Basso et al., 2013). *T. gondii* specific IgG antibodies are known to persist for life in humans (Villard et al., 2016). In experimental studies, where infected pigs were followed for 2.5 months (Basso et al., 2013) and for up to 4 months post infection (Lind et al., 1997), IgG antibodies fluctuated, but remained above the cut-off value during the follow-up months. Hence, presence of antibodies against *T. gondii* indicates an animal was infected by the parasite at some stage of its life. A strong correlation between seropositivity and presence of *T. gondii* in pigs has been established via bioassay in cats (Gamble et al., 2005), although viable *T. gondii* have also been isolated from seronegative pigs (Dubey et al., 2002). It is not known for how long a pig can remain seropositive for *T. gondii*. However, in an experimental study, infected pigs have been found to contain infectious cysts for up to approximately 875 days, which is far beyond the average age of finisher pigs raised for market (Dubey et al., 1986; Dubey, 1988).

Pigs naturally infected with *T. gondii* rarely show clinical signs of disease (Dubey, 2009b; Dubey et al., 2020). However, experimental studies on sows infected with *T. gondii* provide evidence for the occurrence of fever and inappetence (Dubey et al., 1990; Wingstrand et al., 1997). Studies have also reported infections in pregnant sows resulting in abortions, mummified fetuses, stillborn births, and weak piglets (Kim et al., 2009; Basso et al., 2015). There is no evidence to suggest that *T. gondii* infection spreads directly between pigs, other than through the transplacental infection of piglets or infection through cannibalism of infected conspecifics (Dubey, 1988; Ortega-Pacheco et al., 2013; Basso et al., 2015).

Two recent serological surveys on pigs delivered to Danish slaughterhouses have found a higher apparent seroprevalence of *T. gondii* in indoor sows than in indoor finishers. Kofoed et al. (2017) and (Olsen et al., 2020) found 34% and 19%, respectively, in sows, and 3% and 2%, respectively, in finishers. Sows are reared for breeding and are thus sent to slaughter at an older age when compared to the finishers, which are slaughtered for their meat at the age of 6 months. Therefore, a higher prevalence of *T. gondii* in sows could simply be due to a cumulative effect of age from a longer period of constant exposure. But there could also be an increased risk related to housing and management of sows (Kofoed et al., 2017). However, there is little information in the literature on why sows are at more risk than finishers, and when sows are at risk of becoming infected.

Our objectives with the present observational longitudinal study were: (a) to quantify the incidence of *T. gondii* in different age-groups of sows, (b) to investigate the temporal dynamics of the antibody response and the duration for which the sows remained seropositive, c) to investigate if parasitemia could be detected with real-time PCR in blood from recently infected sows.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Description of the farms

An exploratory observational longitudinal study was conducted on four large conventional sow farms. Sow farmers willing to participate in the study from the Mid-Jutland region in Denmark were selected in a convenient way based on contact with the local pig veterinarian. On the four farms (A, B, C, D), gilts and sows, hereafter referred to as sows, were raised in controlled housing conditions and did not have access to outdoor facilities. All sows in the study were housed in either of the following sections of the farm building: The farrowing crates with suckling piglets, the insemination stalls, or the gestation section in a group-housing system. The approximate number of sows present was highest on Farm D (n = 1800), followed by Farm A (n = 1300), Farm B (n = 800) and Farm C (n = 500). All four farms were SPF farms and used some sort of professionally managed rodent control such as traps and or

poison for rodent control. In addition to the above measures for rodent control, Farm C also had two cats for a limited period (for at least 4 months during the study period) housed together with the sows, with no access to outdoors.

2.2. Sample size and collection

Farmer's consent was obtained regarding the use of the samples and the associated data for the present study. Due to logistical constraints, the number of farms selected in the study were limited to four. On each farm, 80 sows were sampled, with 20 sows in each of the four age-cohorts i.e., 6, 12, 18, and 24-months old as the approximate age at the time of first sampling on April 1, 2019. Sows that were easiest to catch were selected and were given an ear-tag containing a unique number for easy identification. The blood sample collection for the study was approved by the Animal Experimentation Council, Ministry of Environment and Food of Denmark (2019-15-0201-01621). The longitudinal study ended in March 2020. During the study period of 1 year, each sow was sampled for blood 11 times, at an interval of 5 weeks. The blood samples were taken from *Vena jugularis* using 4 mL EDTA vacutainer tubes. Sows were sampled over 2 consecutive days, with sampling of two farms per day. All blood samples were kept cool and transported in Styrofoam boxes to Statens Serum Institut, Denmark, for subsequent analysis. At the laboratory, the blood samples were centrifuged, and the separated plasma was collected in Eppendorf tubes and frozen at -20°C until further analysis. Therefore, serology was always done using frozen samples thawed at room temperature and never on fresh samples.

2.3. Laboratory analyses

2.3.1. Initial ELISA test

All plasma samples were tested within 1 or 2 weeks, for IgG antibodies against *T. gondii* according to the manufacturer's instructions (PrioCheck Porcine Toxoplasma Ab) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, 2020). As recommended by the manufacturer, the plasma serology results were expressed as percentage of positivity (PP) relative to the reaction of the positive control. For the cut-off value, we used ≥ 27.7 PP instead of the manufacturer's recommended cut-off of 20 PP, as the former cut-off value has been found to be optimal in previous work (Olsen et al., in preparation). For the initial testing, kits from two different lot numbers were used i.e., visit no. 1 through 6 were tested using lot no. TX180901 L, and visit no. 7 through 11 were tested using lot no. TX190401 L.

2.3.2. Retesting of a subset of samples with three different serology-based tests

To assess the reliability of the results, a subset of the plasma samples was tested at the end of the study (samples were 2–14 months old). Samples were tested in parallel using three different commercial serological tests i.e., PrioCheck-ELISA, Toxo-screen-DA-MAT and LDBio-WB. Due to financial constraints, not all samples could be tested in triplicate. For retesting, 200 plasma samples were selected using simple random stratified sampling method in R statistical software (R Core Team, 2020). Using the initial ELISA PP values, 12 strata were created (<5 PP, 5–10 PP, 10.1–15 PP, 15.1–20 PP, 20.1–25 PP, 25.1–30 PP, 30.1–40 PP, 40.1–65 PP, 65.1–90 PP, 90.1–115 PP, 115.1–140 PP, >140 PP), where 26 samples were intended to be randomly selected from each stratum. Hence, the 200 samples may have included samples from the same animal obtained from different sampling days. If the number of samples in a stratum were less than the required sample size, then all available samples were selected.

When repeating the ELISA test, the samples were tested as described above using kits from lot no. TX 191001 L. The MAT test was run following the manufacturer's instructions. A diluting buffer containing 2-mercaptoethanol, provided with the kit, was added to suppress the IgM-mediated agglutination (Sroka et al., 2008). The samples were tested at two dilutions; 1:40 and 1:4000. The samples were classified as

positive at 1:40 dilution, when agglutinated mat covered at least half of the U-shaped well in the microtitration plate (Sroka et al., 2008). The WB test was also run as per the manufacturer's recommendations. However, the kit was adapted for testing samples from pigs, where the controls and conjugate vials provided with the kit were replaced with our own materials. For the positive and negative controls during the sample runs, a positive and a negative sample, respectively, from previous studies were used (Lind et al., 1997; Kofoed et al., 2017). Moreover, the anti-human IgG conjugate was replaced with rabbit anti-pig IgG peroxidase conjugate (Sigma-Aldrich, A5670). For the dilution of the conjugate (1:4000 concentration), the conjugate buffer solution provided with the kit was used. The reaction time with the substrate during each run was set to 20 min. In humans, a positive immunoblot result for *T. gondii* as per the manufacturer was defined by the presence of three bands i.e., 30 kDa band along with two other bands among 31 kDa, 33 kDa, 40 kDa, and 45 kDa (Franck et al., 2008). However, in our study on pigs, we based a positive result in the presence of bands in the positive control i.e., when the 30 kDa band was observed together with either 31 kDa or 33 kDa band. Additionally, we confirmed the absence of these bands in the negative control. Though the antigenic composition of these bands is unknown (Khammari et al., 2014), the presence of only 30 kDa, 31 kDa and 33 kDa *Toxoplasma* antigen bands in LDBio has shown to be useful in confirming *T. gondii* infections in humans (Khammari et al., 2013). Therefore, the presence of these antigenic bands was also used to confirm a positive immunoblot in pigs (personal communication with Denis Limonne from LDBio diagnostics).

2.3.3. Real-time PCR

To test for parasitemia, the blood samples stored at -20°C in EDTA tubes from acutely infected sows (based on initial ELISA findings) were analyzed with real-time PCR. From each seroconverted sow, three consecutive blood samples i.e., the blood sample taken at the visit prior to the detection of the seroconversion, together with the blood sample from the time of the seroconversion, and the blood sample taken at the visit after the seroconversion were tested. The blood samples were thawed and subsequently prepared and analyzed at Statens Serum Institut, Copenhagen.

From each sample, DNA was extracted from the whole blood following the manufacturer's specific protocol (cat. no./ref. 51306) for QIAamp Mini Kit (QIAGEN, 2016). Following the extraction, real-time PCR was done targeting the 529-bp DNA using the method previously described by Homan et al. (2000). However, this method was modified as described in Reischl et al. (2003), where we used the forward sequence primer 5'CTT GGA GGA GAG ATA TCA GGA CTG T-3' and the reverse sequence primer 5'TCG TCG CTT CCC AAC CA-3' in combination with the internal probe 5-FAM-ATG AAG GCG AGG GTG AGG ATG AGG G BHQ-1-3'.

2.4. Data analysis

2.4.1. Seropositive pigs and mortality

The PrioCheck ELISA test data from the initial testing of 320 sows (serodata) had the following variables: farm ID (A, B, C, D), animal ID (1–80 on each farm), age-cohort number, and resulting PP values for each of the visits (visit 1–11). Mortality in sows was regarded as loss to follow-up in the study and was recorded as the number of sows that had died unassisted, or were euthanized, or sent to slaughter.

The data on the 200 retested samples from sows using three tests (retest data) had the following variables: farm ID, animal ID, ELISA PP values from the initial run, ELISA PP values from the retest, MAT result (0 = negative, 1 = positive) and WB result (0 = negative, 1 = positive). The retested samples were considered positive, if they tested positive simultaneously in ELISA and in at least one of the two other tests, MAT or WB.

To compare results of the initial ELISA with the ELISA retest, and to compare the results from all three diagnostic tests, we calculated the

agreement as the proportion of samples with identical results (i.e., all negative or all positive) in different serological tests.

2.4.2. Weekly incidence rate in different age-cohorts and time-to-event analysis

For incidence rate calculation, a sow was considered seropositive if it had tested positive for *T. gondii* in the initial ELISA analysis. The weekly incidence rate was derived by calculating the total number of seroconverted sows in each age-cohort divided by the total number of weeks of exposure (i.e., time at risk) in all sows in that cohort (Houe et al., 2004). Hence, sows that already tested positive during the first visit (i.e., at time interval 0), were not included in the calculation. The total number of weeks of exposure in all sows from each age-cohort was calculated for the 50-week period. In each 5-week period, sows that were lost to follow-up, were accounted for in the calculation by taking the data for these sows from the preceding period, where sow's infection status was known. And for the sows that seroconverted, we assumed that the sow had seroconverted halfway into the 5-week period (Houe et al., 2004). The weekly incidence rate for each age-cohort was reported along with the exact confidence interval limits, using the method suggested by Ulm (1990).

The disadvantages of simple incidence rate calculations are that they exclude animals that are already positive at the start of the study, and discard information relating to the time of seroconversion i.e. whether these animals seroconvert early or late in the study period (Houe et al., 2004). Therefore, to quantify the relationship between age of pigs and the risk of seroconverting, we also did a time-to-event analysis including the date of all observations for each animal up to (and including) their first positive test, which therefore was able to take into account censoring. Specifically, we used a parametric time-to-event model to investigate whether the hazard of acquiring *T. gondii* infections changes with age. In this analysis, the observations were classified according to censoring as follows: (i) sows that became positive before the first visit (left-censored), (ii) sows that were negative at the first visit and became positive before one of the subsequent visits (interval-censored), and (iii) animals that were not positive at any time point during the study (right-censored). Because the animals were visited with 5-weeks interval during the 1-year follow-up, it was assumed that the interval-censored observations occurred at an unknown time point between the relevant pair of observation points.

For the time-to-event analysis, we created a new dataset (Supplementary material I) from the "serodata", that included age-cohort information, farm ID, and left bound and right bound values for the time interval (the sow's age in weeks) for each of the 320 sows in the study. The definition of various variables in the time-to-event analysis dataset is given in a table in Supplementary material II. Sows from 6, 12, 18 and 24-months age-cohort were assumed to be approximately 26.1 weeks, 52.2 weeks, 78.3 weeks, and 104.4 weeks, respectively, at the time of entry into the study i.e., at visit 1. Furthermore, visit 1 corresponded to week number 5, visit 2 to week number 10, visit 3 to week number fifteen and so on to include a total of 50 weeks of follow-up during the period of 1 year. Therefore, for example, if a sow from the 6-month age-cohort tested positive for the first time during visit 10, then the left and the right bound of the time interval would be its approximate age at those two points in the interval, which corresponds to 66.1 and 71.1 weeks, respectively. The data were analyzed using a parametric time-to-event model with a Weibull distribution response, and age cohort within farm as a random effect. The estimate of the shape parameter (ρ) of the Weibull distribution was used to evaluate whether the hazard decreased ($\rho < 1$) or increased ($\rho > 1$) with increasing age of the sows. The model was fitted within a Bayesian framework using JAGS (Plummer, 2003) interfaced using the "runjags" package (Denwood, 2016) for R (R Core Team, 2020). We assumed that the risk of becoming infected with *T. gondii* in sows below the age of 6 months may be low, and that the model may therefore be sensitive to the selected "start age" for the risk period of seroconversion. Therefore, two separate models were fitted,

one using the birth age i.e., at week zero and the second at 6 months i.e., at 26 weeks as the minimum possible age for seroconversion (R script, Supplementary material III).

For the estimation of the incidence rate and the time-to-event analysis, we used the initial ELISA results for all data points, because the 200 out of the initial 2989 samples that were retested in ELISA or tested in MAT and WB were chosen based on the original values, and we would therefore expect to introduce a bias if using the retest data for these 200 samples.

3. Results

3.1. Plasma samples

In total, 2989 blood samples were collected from the 320 sows during the 11 visits to the four farms, and the samples were initially tested with ELISA. During the 1-year follow-up, 88 sows (28%) were removed from the study either because they had died unassisted on the farm (n = 23), were euthanized (n = 12) or sent to slaughter (n = 47). For six sows, the reason for their removal was not registered. Additionally, 87 sows could not be sampled for blood on the day of the visit, either because they could not be located or an ethical decision was taken not to sample them, because they were farrowing, were sick, injured, or due to difficulties in drawing blood. Also, during the last visit (visit 11) in March 2020, sows from farm D could not be sampled due to COVID-19 restrictions; and hence, these were reported as missing data. Out of the four farms, only one farm (Farm C) had registered the specific reason for euthanasia or slaughter of the sows on the farm.

3.2. Seropositive sows

Among the 320 sows, 24 tested positive at least once for *T. gondii* during the 11 visits to the farms i.e., four from farm A, nine from farm B, four from farm C, and seven from farm D. Out of the 24 seropositive sows, eight tested positive for *T. gondii* at the start of the study, and the remaining 16 tested positive once or more during the 10 following visits (Fig. 1). However, only five out of these 16 sows remained seropositive throughout the study (Fig. 2). And amongst these five sows, one from the 6-month age-cohort became positive during the final visit, hence the future antibody dynamics were not known. Additionally, out of the eight sows that tested positive for *T. gondii* at first survey, only seven remained seropositive throughout the follow-up period (Fig. 3).

3.3. *T. gondii* incidence rate in age-cohorts and time-to-event analysis

The 95% confidence intervals for the weekly incidence rate of *T. gondii* between the four age cohorts overlapped widely. Weekly incidence was highest in the 24-month age-cohort (IR = 0.0023, 95% CI = 0.0010 – 0.0051) followed by the 6-month (IR = 0.0017, 95% CI = 0.0008 – 0.0037), 12 month (IR = 0.0009, 95% CI = 0.0003 – 0.0027) and the 18-month age-cohort (IR = 0.0003, 95% CI = 0.0000 – 0.0018). The incidence rate did not show any obvious temporal pattern or clustering with time, although the 95% CI were too wide to be able to reliably conclude that sows had acquired the infection independently of each other.

The results from the time-to-event analysis models produced estimates for rho as 2.1 (95% CI = 1.3 – 3.0) and 1.3 (95% CI = 0.7 – 1.8),

Fig. 1. *Toxoplasma gondii* IgG antibody dynamics in individual sows during the one-year longitudinal survey of 320 sows from four large breeding farms in Denmark. The sows belonged to one of the four age-cohorts i.e., 6, 12, 18 and 24 months (approximate age at the time of the first blood sample collection). From each age-cohort, 20 sows were repeatedly sampled during the eleven visits (x-axis), which were scheduled at regular 5-week intervals. Only sows testing positive in at least one sample (n = 24) during the initial testing with the PrioCheck test are shown. The cut-off used for the ELISA PrioCheck test was ≥ 27.7 PP.

Fig. 2. Time of seroconversion in each truly seroconverted sow during the one-year longitudinal survey of 320 sows from four large breeding farms in Denmark. Each line represents a seroconverted sow (n = 5) from farm B and D, where sows 10B and 11B belong to the 6-month age-cohort, 58D to the 18-month, and 68B and 73B to the 24-month age-cohort. A sow was considered to have truly seroconverted, when the ELISA percent of positive control (PP) value (y-axis) of the sow was above the cut-off of ≥ 27.7 (red dotted line) and continued to remain above the cut-off throughout the sampling period. The black arrows represent the ELISA PP values from the retest, confirming the seroconversion status of sow 73B, where the PP values from the initial ELISA test briefly fell below the cut-off.

Fig. 3. Longitudinally surveyed sows of four different age groups (approximately 6, 12, 18, and 24 months at the time of first sampling) during the eleven visits (x-axis) at four Danish sow breeding farms. Eight sows (out of 320) tested positive at the start of the study; and seven of these remained positive throughout the study. Four of the seropositive sows (61B, 80B, 66C, 64D, 80D) were from 24-month age-cohort, two from 18-month age-cohort (53C, 58C), and one sow (29B) from 12-month age-cohort. A sow was considered positive at ELISA percent of positive control (PP) value (y-axis) of ≥ 27.7 PP (red-dotted line).

when assuming that the risk period for seroconversion begins at birth and at 6 months, respectively. These median estimates for rho are both above 1, which suggests that the hazard (instantaneous risk) of seroconversion increases with age. A graphical illustration of the relationship between age and seroconversion implied by these models is given in Fig. 4. Furthermore, the lower 95% CI is above 1, when assuming that the risk period for seroconversion begins at birth. However, the 95% CI includes 1, when assuming that the risk period for seroconversion begins at 6 months.

3.4. Results from retesting

3.4.1. Comparison of ELISA results after retesting

Retesting 200 samples with ELISA showed an agreement of 91%, (Fig. 5). In line, the PP values from the initial testing and the retesting with ELISA were highly correlated (Spearman correlation = 0.88). Nine out of the twelve samples that tested positive in the initial testing, tested negative with much lower PP values during the retest. Additionally, these nine samples tended to group with the 17 other samples that tested negative in both the initial and the retesting, but that also had substantially lower PP values in the retest (Fig. 5. observations within the circle).

3.4.2. Comparison of ELISA results with MAT and WB

Out of the 200 stratified random samples, a high agreement of 93% between the three test outcomes were observed i.e., 118 samples simultaneously tested negative and 68 samples simultaneously tested positive in ELISA, MAT and WB (Table 1).

3.5. Detection of parasitemia

All samples tested to detect parasitemia were negative in real-time PCR.

4. Discussion

The aim of this study was to understand why sows appeared to have a higher risk of being seropositive for *T. gondii* than finishing pigs. To elucidate this, we explored the *T. gondii* antibody dynamics following natural infection in sows. This knowledge was acquired by taking blood samples repeatedly from the same sows belonging to different age groups and testing them for the presence of *T. gondii* antibodies. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to have explored the *T. gondii* seroconversion dynamics in sows over a long time following natural exposure. The purpose of the study design was to describe and reveal transmission patterns in time and with age and not to estimate the national seroconversion rate in large intensive sow herds in Denmark.

4.1. Toxoplasma gondii infections in sows

In the present study, the infection pressure was lower than expected, as only five sows out of 320 seroconverted and remained seropositive throughout the study period of 1 year (Fig. 2) and 16 sows apparently seroconverted, but subsequently underwent seroreversion (Fig. 1). Moreover, seven out of the eight sows that were positive since the beginning of the study, continued to remain positive until the end (Fig. 3). All the sows that stayed seropositive throughout the study tested positive simultaneously in ELISA and in at least one of the two other tests, MAT or WB. Hosts infected with *T. gondii* are believed to remain seropositive for life (Tenter et al., 2000). Experimental studies of 3–4 months duration have reported a rise in the antibody concentrations approximately at 2-weeks post infection and the infected pigs remained positive post seroconversion until the end of the study (Lind et al., 1997; Basso et al., 2013). However, in these studies, pigs were infected with large doses of oocysts or tachyzoites, and therefore, infections in these experimentally infected pigs may not simulate natural infections. The sows in our study, which did not consistently test positive for *T. gondii* (Fig. 1), may represent false positive results. However, with the present data, we are unable to confirm this. False positive results in ELISA may occur due to cross-reactivity from preexisting antibodies, which has previously been documented for a closely related parasite, *Sarcocystis miescheriana* (Lind et al., 1997). Moreover, sows (n = 2) that subsequently tested negative in ELISA only for a few months (Figs. 2 and 3), may represent false negative results as these samples tested positive throughout the series with MAT and/or WB tests. This would be in line with Dubey et al. (2002) who found that 2 out of 55 pigs in a study tested

Fig. 4. Results of the time-to-event models based on interval censored observations. The upper panels show the instantaneous hazard (rate, y-axis) for acquiring *Toxoplasma gondii* infection as a function of age (in weeks, x-axis) assuming that the earliest age at which animals are at risk of seroconversion is birth (left) or from 6 months (right). The lower panels show the probability of being seronegative (one minus the cumulative incidence, y-axis) for *Toxoplasma gondii* as a function of age (in days, x-axis), based on the same assumptions. The median estimates are shown as black lines, and the grey shaded areas show 95% confidence intervals for the relationships.

Fig. 5. Scatter plot showing the ELISA percent of positive control (PP) values from the retest (y-axis) as a function of the PP values from the initial testing (x-axis) with the ELISA-PrioCheck test. From the initial ELISA testing, 200 samples were stratified and randomly selected and retested. Both the initial and the retesting of the plasma samples were performed using the same cut-off of ≥ 27.7 PP, where the cut-offs are represented on the respective axes with a black dotted line. The PP values are displayed on a base-10 log scale of x and y axes. The diagonal dotted line indicates perfect agreement between test. Inserted are the numbers of samples with perfect agreements (both negative or both positive) and the numbers of samples that disagreed between tests. Samples within the circle indicate a cluster of 26 samples which had considerably lower PP values during retesting.

Table 1

Observed frequency of each combination of test results from three serological tests when testing 200 plasma samples from sows from four large Danish conventional sow breeding farms. The first and the last row shows samples with perfect agreement between the three tests (negative and positive, respectively). A perfect agreement is calculated as a proportion of samples with identical results (i.e., all negative or all positive) in the three different serological tests.

ELISA ^a	MAT ^b	WB ^c	N ^d
0	0	0	118
0	0	1	1
0	1	0	2
0	1	1	0
1	0	0	6
1	0	1	3
1	1	0	2
1	1	1	68
			200

^a Enzyme linked immunoassay, PrioCHECK® Toxoplasma Ab porcine (ThermoFisher Scientific) at a cut-off value of ≥ 27.7 PP.

^b Modified agglutination test, Toxo-Screen DA (bioMerieux).

^c Western blot test, LDBio-Toxo II IgG (LDBIO Diagnostics).

^d Number of samples in each of the test combination.

seronegative in both MAT and WB but tested positive in cat bioassay. Interfering substances in the samples can lead to both false positive and negative results in assays (Tate and Ward, 2004). In certain individuals, these interfering substances vary occasionally and cannot be avoided (Tate and Ward, 2004). Still, for most of the samples, there was a high agreement and correlation between test and retest using ELISA.

During retesting, we found a high agreement (93%) between the results of ELISA, MAT and WB tests. In an unpublished study, we compared the performance of these three tests and found that there was 94% agreement between the results at 27.7 PP (Olsen et al., in preparation). In previous studies, MAT has been used as a reference test at a cut-off value of 1:40 to evaluate the performance of other diagnostic tests in pigs (Steinparzer et al., 2015; Felin et al., 2017) and to diagnose *T. gondii* infections in naturally infected sows (Santoro et al., 2017). A previous study has found detectable antibodies with a high agreement in bioassay in cats using a lower titer of 1:10 (Dubey et al., 2002). However, since we wanted to evaluate the results from ELISA using MAT as one of the reference tests, we aimed to reduce false positive results, and therefore, chose a relatively conservative cut-off. The WB test used in our study was developed for testing human sera and to the best of our knowledge, it has not been tested on pigs. However, in our unpublished study, we have found the performance of this test to be acceptable, as also shown in the high agreement between the test results.

The reproducibility of ELISA results was not perfect as 18 samples (from 11 animals) varied between the initial testing and the retesting, where the positive sows tested negative during retest or vice-versa (Supplementary material IV). We could not ascribe the cause for the divergent results to specific plates when repeating ELISA. However, since the initial ELISA testing and the retesting were carried out using kits with different lot numbers, maybe a part of the differences in the results could be related to the lots.

Additionally, we found that PP values in seronegative sows (those below the cut-off of 27.7 PP) increased with age (Supplementary material V). These results are consistent with findings from a previous study, where seronegative sows had significantly higher PP values compared to seronegative finishers (Olsen et al., 2020). Hence, these results may suggest an age-related increase in cross-reactive antibodies, and this may increase the risk of false positive results in older animals. Therefore, ELISA test characteristics, and reproducibility as well as increasing antibody levels in negative pigs, should be taken into consideration if planning future surveillance of *T. gondii* based on serology.

4.2. *Toxoplasma gondii* incidence

In both humans and animals, *T. gondii* seroprevalence is known to increase with age (Wilking et al., 2016; Stelzer et al., 2019). Among pigs, sows have a higher probability of testing seropositive for *T. gondii* than finishers, and this has been attributed to prolonged exposure (Kofoed et al., 2017). However, it may be that incidence itself increases with age and this could be because of differences in the housing, feed type/amount consumed and hygiene management during different phases of production. In our study, we estimated *T. gondii* incidence rate in four different age-cohorts, and to our knowledge, such age-specific data are not available from previous studies. We used the weekly incidence estimates in each age-cohort to roughly predict the proportion of infected sows at the approximate age of slaughter ($t = 130$ weeks) by calculating the number of sows that had seroconverted at time t ($1 - (e^{-IR \times t})$) in each age-cohort (Houe et al., 2004). By assuming the incidence rate to be constant and independent of age, we predicted the average proportion of positive sows to be 14% (range 4% – 23%) at 130 weeks (2.5 years). In this study, we found that 11 out of 16 sows were only testing positive for a short period, so these sows may not be expected to test positive for *T. gondii* if slaughtered at 2.5 years of age. Therefore, we expect the seroprevalence at slaughter in sows from the four sampled farms to be even lower than estimated (14%), and thus lower than reported seroprevalence of 34% and 19% in the previous two Danish studies (Kofoed et al., 2017). However, the present study is different in several important ways in comparison with the previous two Danish studies i.e., Kofoed et al. (2017) and Olsen et al. (2020). In the previous studies, sows were sampled, after they had been euthanized at the slaughterhouses, whereas, in the present study, live sows were sampled on farms. Therefore, the sows in this study were on an average younger, and thus less likely to have been exposed to *T. gondii*. Additionally, in the Kofoed et al. (2017) study, the estimated seroprevalence was based on a non-stratified sampling of sows from sixteen small to medium-sized farms (Kofoed and Vorlund-Kiær, 2016), where the rate of infection has been shown to be higher when compared to large-sized farms (Djokic et al., 2016). Hence, we speculate that the uncertainty arising from the limited number of farms, combined with the large sizes of the herds and the younger age of sows in this study may explain for the lower observed prevalence. And lastly, since the four farms in this study were selected non-randomly, it could also be that we selected farms with relatively low prevalence, when compared to an average Danish sow farm.

The incidence rate estimates in the four age-cohorts were wide and overlapping and thus, did not conclusively indicate an effect of age on *T. gondii* incidence. We therefore additionally implemented a time-to-event analysis, including additional data on sows that were already positive during the first sampling, and also imposing additional assumptions regarding the permanency of seroconversion as well as the form of the true (unobserved) distribution of times between birth/6 months and sero-conversion (Weibull distribution). We found that the model was sensitive to the age at which we assumed animals began to be at risk of seroconversion: the instantaneous hazard rate for acquiring *T. gondii* infection was estimated to have a stronger relationship with age when the start age was assumed to be at birth ($\rho = 2.1$, 95% CI = 1.3 – 3.0) compared to when we assumed that seroconversion could not happen before 6 months of age ($\rho = 1.3$, 95% CI = 0.7 – 1.8). And indeed, none of the 80 sows tested positive when they were sampled the first time at the age of six months. Part of the difference between these models may be attributable to the sampling scheme: because as sows were not sampled before 6 months of age, it was only possible to detect permanent seroconversions and not temporary seroconversions in sows below 6 months of age. In sows older than 6 months, however, seroconversions could be detected every 5 weeks via regular surveys, thus detecting both temporary and permanent seroconversions. Therefore, the observed increase in incidence with age may partly be an artefact of the increased probability of detecting temporary seroconversions in the

older sows that were sampled more intensively. However, it is also possible that the true age effect contains a “step change” in the hazard of seroconversion that occurs at around 5–6 months of age i.e., when the gilts are selected for breeding. More data would be required to determine the precise nature of this relationship.

The strength of the present study in comparison with a seroprevalence study is that the study design allowed us to determine whether the *T. gondii* infections occurred sporadically or at a specific age e.g., caused by the specific management of a certain age group or if the infections occurred at a specific point in time e.g., due to feed or water contamination with the oocysts or due to farm cats being infected and excreting oocysts in the stables for a short period. The prevalence of permanent seroconversions in this study was lower than expected and all occurred in sows that were at least above the age of 1 year. Hence, the observed apparent random pattern suggests that the risk of infection in these four sow farms occurs at an individual animal level rather than as a risk factor that simultaneously affects the entire farm or a specific age group. Thus, the risk could e.g. be related to the random chance of a sow catching and eating an infected mouse.

4.3. Detection of parasitemia

We were not able to detect *T. gondii* DNA in the blood samples of sows that had acquired infection during the study period. The use of real-time PCR method to find circulating *T. gondii* DNA in blood samples is used in humans (Edvinsson et al., 2006); however, to best of our knowledge, this approach has not previously been used to demonstrate parasitemia in pigs. In pigs, parasitemia has been demonstrated by inoculating mice with blood samples from infected animals (Moura et al., 2007; Klun et al., 2011). At present, there is limited information on the occurrence and the duration of parasitemia in pigs. Parasitemia has been detected at 7th day post infection with oocysts, and on the 3rd and the 49th day post infection with bradyzoites in an experimental infection study on boars (Moura et al., 2007). Additionally, frequent occurrence of parasitemia has been observed in naturally infected pigs at the time of slaughter (Klun et al., 2011). The duration of parasitemia in hosts is brief, and hence can be difficult to detect in blood (Tenter et al., 2000). And since we sampled sows only at every 5-week intervals, it is likely that these sows may have been aparasitemic at the time of the sample collections.

5. Conclusion

Sixteen seroconversions were detected in the 1-year follow-up period. We observed two patterns of seroconversions in sows: those that remained positive in ELISA while others that rapidly returned to being seronegative. In the latter group, ELISA positive results could not be confirmed in MAT or WB. Our study shows fewer seroconversions in sows than expected, when looking at seroprevalence estimates in the slaughtered sows from the recent two Danish studies. Our time-to-event analysis suggested that there could be a relationship between age and instantaneous risk of seroconversion, but the results were not conclusive. We did not detect parasitemia in recently seroconverted sows. In our study, nine percent of the ELISA results were found to be discordant during retesting. This should be taken into consideration in future surveys on sows.

Author contributions

Abbey Olsen: conceptualization, methodology, investigation, data curation, statistical analysis, original draft preparation, review, and editing. **Lis Alban:** conceptualization, methodology, review and editing, supervision, funding acquisition. **Matthew Denwood:** methodology, statistical analysis, supervision, review, and editing. **Hans Houe:** conceptualization, methodology, supervision, review, and editing. **Tina Birk Jensen:** conceptualization, methodology, review & editing,

supervision, funding acquisition. **Henrik Vedel Nielsen:** conceptualization, methodology, review & editing, supervision, funding acquisition.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

Abbey Olsen, Lis Alban, and Tina Birk Jensen work for an organization that offers advice to farmers and abattoirs.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary material related to this article can be found, in the online version, at doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vetpar.2021.109460>.

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